

Adaptive mixed reality squat training based on real-time physiological feedback

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Introduction

In recent years, Mixed Reality (MR) has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing physical training by providing immersive, interactive, and adaptive environments. Unlike traditional training methods, which often lack personalization and real-time feedback, MR enables the integration of dynamic systems that can respond to individual user needs [1]. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) and Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) metrics can be used to dynamically adjust training difficulty based on the user's physical and cognitive state in MR environments, enabling real-time adaptation. This pilot study describes the implementation of an MR squat training scenario whose difficulty is adjusted in real-time based on physiological measurements recorded with wearable sensors.

Methods

ElectroCardioGraphic (ECG) and GSR data were recorded through a pair of wearable sensors (Shimmer Sensing, Ireland). The proposed system is implemented within an MR environment (HTC Vive XR Elite) and follows a structured two-phase protocol (**Figure 1**). (1) **Calibration**: during a baseline light squat period, root mean square of successive differences (RMSSD) and standard deviation of NN intervals (SDNN) from HRV, skin conductance response (SCR) amplitude and SCR number of peaks from GSR were collected every 20 s. Personalized reference ranges of each metric were defined as mean \pm 0.5 std [2]. (2) **Adaptive MR training**: participants engage in the MR squat training for 4 min. The training program comprises three difficulty levels ranging from easy (under-challenged) to difficult (over-challenged), achieved by manipulating height and frequency of the virtual obstacles. Every 20 s, an algorithm evaluates whether current metric values fall within the reference ranges established during the MR calibration and accordingly adjusts the level of difficulty.

Figure 1.

Results

In this pilot study, 3 healthy participants (24,36 and 40 yo, 1 F) completed the protocol. Over the 4-min session, participants experienced different levels of difficulty, demonstrating the system's ability to personalize the training program. In total, an average of 4 adaptation events per participant were observed, with real-time adjustments triggering transitions between intensity levels.

Discussion

This pilot study suggests the feasibility of an adaptive MR squat training system, which dynamically adjusts difficulty based on real-time physiological measurements. The system's ability to maintain participants in an "appropriately challenged" zone could enhance training engagement and effectiveness while avoiding under or over-exertion. Further developments will integrate biomechanical and performance metrics, to adjust the difficulty also based on the subject's squat execution quality.

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